

KURASHCHILARNING TEXNIK TAYYORGARLIGINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHDA MAXSUS MASHQLARNING AHAMIYATI

Termiz davlat pedagogika instituti
Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlar nazariyasi va
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***Annotatsiya:** Ushbu maqolada kurashchilarning texnik tayyorgarligini takomillashtirishda maxsus mashqlarning ahamiyati hamda maxsus mashqlardan foydalanishning texnologiyalari to'g'risida ma'lumotlar keltirilgan.*

***Kalit so'zlar:** kurash sport turi, texnik harakat, maxsus mashqlar, texnik usullar, takomillashtirish, kurashchi.*

Bugungi kunga kelib 3500 yillik tarixga ega bo'lgan kurash milliy sport turimizga hukumatimiz tomonidan katta e'tibor qaratilmoqda. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2020-yil 4-noyabrdagi "Kurash milliy sport turini rivojlantirish va uning xalqaro nufuzini yanada oshirish chora-tadbirlari to'g'risida"gi PQ 4881-son qarorini misol keltirishimiz mumkin.

Kurashchilarning yanada yuqoriroq natijalarga erishishi uchun ko'plab yuqori talablar qo'yilmoqda. Ularning tayyorgarlik jarayoni va o'quv mashg'ulotlar tuzilishidagi vazifalarni qayta ko'rib chiqish hamda o'rganish muammolari yuzaga kelmoqda.

Xususan bugungi kunda kurashchilarning texnik tayyorgarligidagi ba'zi kamchiliklarni ko'rish mumkin. Kurashchilar musobaqalarda turli texnik usullarni ketma-ket amalga oshiruvchilar soni kamchilikni tashkil qiladi. Ular bellashuvlarda yuqori darajadagi texnik harakatlar bilan kurashishlarini ko'rish kamdan kam hollarda uchramoqda. Hozirgi kunda texnik harakatlarni takomillashtirib borish va uning texnologiyasini ishlab chiqish dolzarb masala xisoblanadi.

Tadqiqot ob'yekti va predmetining belgilanishi: Kurashchilarning texnik tayyorgarligida maxsus mashqlarning ahamiyati.

Kurashchilar o'quv-mashg'ulot jarayonining vositasi va tuzilmasi.

Tadqiqot maqsadi va vazifalari. Ushbu maqolaning asosiy maqsadi kurashchilarning texnik tayyorgarligini maxsus mashqlar yordamida takomillashtirish texnologiyasini ishlab chiqish, umumiy sport natijalariga ijobiy ta'sir etish darajasini yanada ko'tarish.

Kurashchilarni o'quv-mashg'ulot jarayonida qo'llaniladigan samarali maxsus mashqlar majmuasini aniqlash.

Kurashchilarda maxsus mashqlar asosida texnik tayyorgarlikni takomillashtirish texnologiyasini ishlab chiqarish.

Kurashchilarning harakatlarini maxsus mashqlar yordamida texnik tayyorgarlikni takomillashtirish texnologiyasini mutaxassislariga tavsiya etish.

Shu asnoda olib borilgan adabiyot manbalarining tahliliga asoslanib, Kurashchilarning texnik maxoratini oshirishda va jismoniy sifatlarini rivojlantirishda mashg'ulot bosqichlaridagi yuklamalarni me'yorlash muammosini hal etishda quyidagi metodlarini ko'rsatish lozim.

Texnik harakatni takomillashtirishda maxsus mashqlardan foydalanib takomillashtirish asosan mashg'ulot bosqichlarida ularning tuzilmalarida aniqlashtirish va rejalashtirish mumkin. Maxsus va bevosita tayyorgarlik yuklamalarini amalga oshirish muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi.

Kurashchilarni texnik tayyorgarligini takomillashtirishda maxsus mashqlar orqali rivojlantirish dolzarb bo'lib, Kurashchilarni xalqaro nufuzli musobaqalarga tayyorlashda o'ta dolzarb ahamiyat kasb etadi.

Malakali kurashchilarning muvaffaqiyatga erishishi, ularning ish qobiliyatining tayyorgarligiga bevosita bog'liqdir. A.Atoyev, Kerimov F.A., Taymuradov Sh.O., Yusupov K.T lar kurashchilarni tayyorlashda umumiy va maxsus jismoniy tayyorgarlik darajasining beqiyos ahamiyatini ta'kidlab, ushbu

jarayonni texnik tayyorgarlik maxoratini takomillashtirishda asosiy omil bo'lib xizmat qilishini ko'rsatib o'tganlar. Mualliflar kurash bilan shug'ullanuvchi sportchilarda barcha jismoniy sifatlarni rivojlantiruvchi ko'plab umumiy va maxsus mashqlarni hamda ularni qo'llash metodlarini yoritib berganlar.

Natijalar shuni ko'rsatadiki; Mualliflar o'z tadqiqotlari natijalariga asoslanib, kurashchilarni 3 ta shartli guruhga ajratganlar, "tezkor-kuch xususiyatli kurashchilar maxsus chidamkorlik xususiyatiga ega kurashchilar va universal" kurashchilar. Kerimov F.A uzoq yillar davomida turli yoshdagi va turli malakaga ega kurashchilar ustida tadqiqotlar o'tkazish natijasida jismoniy sifatlarning texnik maxoratga va musobaqa (bellashuv) jarayoniga bevosita aloqador ekanligini ta'kidlaydilar. Uning fikricha, jismoniy sifatlarni qanchalik mukammal darajada rivojlangan bo'lsa, sport maxorati ham shunchalik rivojlanib o'sib boradi.

Kurashchilar texnik harakatlarini turlicha bo'limlar va yo'nalishlarda katta amplituda bilan aniq bajarishi, uning takomillashuvining asosiy belgisidir. Cho'ziltiruvchi mashqlar: oddiy, prujinali harakatlar, o'zining muvozzanatini ushlagan holda siltanishli, tashqi yordam bilan bajariladigan harakatlar egiluvchanlikni rivojlantirishning asosiy vositalari hisoblanadi.

Bunday mashqlar bilan shug'ullanish paytida bir qator uslubiy shartlarni bajarish lozim:

- mashqlarni boshlashdan oldin albatta badan qizdirish mashqlarini kiritish;
- aniq maqsadlarni oldinga qo'yish, masalan, gavda yoki buyumning ma'lum bir nuqtasiga qo'lni tekkazish;
- cho'ziltirish mashqlarini ma'lum bir ketma-ketlikda takroriy bajarish: qo'llar uchun, oyoqlar uchun, gavda uchun;
- cho'ziltirish mashqlari takrorlashlari orasida bo'shashtirish mashqlarini bajarish;
- maxsus mashqlarni bajarish vaqtida asta-sekin ularning amplitudasini oshirish;

-maxsus mashqlarni bajarishda shuni hisobga olish kerakki, harakatchanlikni rivojlantirishning eng asosiy metodi - bu takrorlash metodi hisoblanadi.

Bir-ikki oyda har kuni ikki-uch marta shug‘ullanuvchilarning alohida qobiliyatlari va imkoniyatlariga qarab 25-50 takrorlashdan iborat me‘yordagi cho‘ziltirishga qaratilgan maxsus mashqlardantashkil topgan o‘quv-mashg‘ulotlar davomida egiluvchanlik ancha o‘sishi mumkin.

Texnik harakatlarni takomillashtirishda eng avvalo texnik usullarga mos ravishdagi maxsus mashqlarning yuqori tezlikda aniq bajara olishi tushuniladi. Masalan; Yelka usullariga kiruvchi texnik harakatlar uchun sport rezinasi orqali tezlikda va takroriy bajariladigan maxsus mashqlar, Bardor usuliga kiruvchi (ko‘krakdan yoki beldan oshirib tashlash) texnik harakatlarni takomillashtirishda chucheladan foydalanish yoki sherik bilan xuddi shu texnik harakatlarni tez, aniq va takroriy bajarishlar sportchining ulkan yutuqlarida kata ahamiyat kasb etadi.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, olib borilgan adabiyot manbalarining ta‘hliliga asoslanib, kurashchilarning texnik tayyorgarnigini takomillashtirishda maxsus mashqlar ta‘sirida rivojlantirish mashg‘ulot bosqichlaridagi yuklamalarni me‘yorlash muammosini hal etishda yuqorida keltirilgan ilmiy-uslubiy adabiyotlarni o‘rganish va taxlil qilish kurashda texnik harakat malaka va ko‘nikmalarini takomillashtirishda maxsus mashqlar ta‘siri muhim ahamiyatga ega.

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